

SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

SE Project:

Fingerprint Based ATM System

- SRS Document
- Designing
- Testing

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Fingerprint Based ATM Transaction System

CONTENTS-

1 SRS Document	4-13
1.1 Purpose	4
1.2 Scope	4
1.3 Document Overview	4-5
1.4 System Features	5-6
1.4.1 Technical Field	5
1.4.2 System Environment	5-6
1.5 Basic Functionality	6
1.6 User Characteristics	6
1.7 Performance Requirements	6-7
1.8 Budget	7
1.9 Database of the bank	7
1.10 Users Fingerprint	7
1.10.1 Transaction Authentication	7
1.11 Functional Requirements	7-8
1.11.1 Facility of aborting transaction	8
1.11.2 Email code format	8
1.11.3 Facility of email re-entering	8
1.11.4 Denial of specific services, if email goes wrong	8
1.11.5 Register finger	8
1.11.6 Facility of re-entering the finger	8
1.11.7 Denial of service, if fingerprint goes wrong	8
1.12 Non-functional requirements	9-10
1.12.1 Scope	9
1.12.2 Functionality	9
1.12.3 Usability	9
1.12.4 Reliability	9
1.12.5 Performance	9
1.12.6 Security	9-10
1.13 Front End Description	10
1.14 Back End Description	10
1.15 Login Use Case I	11
1.16 Sign Up Use Case II	12
1.17 Authentication Use Case III	13-14
1.18 Our Commitment	14

2 Design Document	15-23
2.1 System Architecture	15
2.1.1 Design Constraints	15
2.1.2 Sequence Diagram	15
2.1.3 Login Sequence Diagram	15
2.1.4 Sign Up Sequence Diagram	15
2.2 Software Interface	16
2.3 Communication Interface	16
2.4 Performance Requirements	16
2.4.1 Performance prerequisite I	16
2.4.2 Performance prerequisite II	16
2.4.3 Performance prerequisite III	16
2.5 Other Requirements	17-23
Use Case Diagram	17
ER Diagram	18
Data Flow Diagram	18
Collaboration Diagram	19
Activity Diagram	20
Sequence Diagram	21-23
State Chart Diagram	23
3 Testing Document	24-29
3.1 Graphical User Interface Testing	24
3.2 Usability Testing	24
3.3 Software Performance Testing	24-25
3.4 Compatibility Testing	25
3.5 Exception Handling	25
3.6 Load Testing	26
3.7 Installation Testing	26
3.8 Testcases	26-28
3.9 Testing and Results	28-29
3.9.1 Performance Testing	28
3.9.2 Security Testing	29
3.9.3 Non-Functional Testing	29
4 References	30

SRS Document

1.1 Purpose

The software requirements specified also provide the complete description of the functions and the specified of the automated transaction system installed within a bank. The purpose of this project is to provide secure access to the automated transaction machines. This requirements specification document defines Exterior Interface, Presentation and Software System Characterizes requirements of automated transaction system incorporated within a machine or a web portal. This document is for the purpose of being used as an official document. The following group is also entitled to this document including but not limited to Developers for the purpose of maintaining the software and new releases of the firmware, Management, Testers and Project Engineers.

1.2 Scope

The Automated Transaction Machine is designed to operate 24/7 and hence allows the bank clients to carry out their small everyday transactions in a secure manner. All data is held and secured at the encrypted database. The user side is connected to the client side using secure protocols over the internet. This software facilitates the user to perform various transactions in his account without going to bank. This software offers benefits such cash withdrawals, balance transfers, deposits, inquiries, credit card advances and other banking related operations for customers. It also allows the administrator to fix the tariffs and rules as and when required. The software takes as input the login Id and the bank account number of the user for login purposes. The outputs then comprise of an interactive display that lets the user select the desirable function that he wants to perform.

1.3 Document Overview

The document is limited to two chapters for the overview of purpose of the document. First, we will provide the full description of the project that is dependent on Fingerprint biometric based automated transaction machines

with state of the art security. The details provided below about the various requirements and various hardware/software are defined below:

Overall Description:

The Automated transaction system incorporates numerous GUI menus as well as the device for fingerprint sensor, to provide high safety. It delivers secure admittance to the account of a client. The Automated transaction system must be able to provide the following facilities to the client:

Enter Email: A customer is required to provide a valid email address throughout the use of his/her account.

Change Email: A customer or user can also change the registered email from his/her account that is also sync with the generated messages.

Enroll Finger: A customer is also required to provide a valid fingerprint message that is used to link as an account extension.

Change Fingerprint: A customer can hence change the fingerprint provided for registration from his/her account.

1.4 System features

1.4.1 Technical Field

The present invention or development of an application system as our project relates to a Biometric fingerprint identification system using a fingerprint for identification of people using fingerprint matching and more particularly to a fingerprint identification system in which a fingerprint identifying function is added to an operating system ("OS") of an electronic money transfer system, or the fingerprint is used a key for a door or the fingerprint is encoded into a cipher key.

1.4.2 System Environment

Most use cases for the project are based on the admin user as most of functionality for the application is on the customer/client side which needs

to be monitored by a moderator or administrator. The administrator will have access to all phases of the application/software and will be able to manage scheduling and generation of emails and text message at run-time on user account access. The customer/client will only be able to confirm transactions based on his/her biometric fingerprints.

1.5 Basic Functionality

Following are the basic functionality of the application:

- Customer to login and view account, make transaction, update and edit different data/records limited to his/her account only.
- Email Scheduling and message generation on run-time.
- Withdrawal and Balance check from account.
- Biometric fingerprint reader and match from database.
- Data and information regarding account credentials stored in fingerprint database.
- Card Rejection on login failure or invalid account credentials.

1.6 User Characteristics.

This application/system has a very simple and easy user interface. The privilege levels are:

- The customer will only be able to make transactions, balance transfer, account info update and delete from his/her account only and will not be allowed privileges except their account limitations.
- Administrator can add and modify any data and Scheduling systems.
- The administrator will be a single entity and will be added to the database.
- The moderator will be able to monitor false use of the current system and will have privilege over ban and summation of the current system.

1.7 Performance Requirements

Since we are developing an application that is optimized in size and consumption of resources, we should not have to worry regarding the

hardware and performance requirement. The recommended system/hardware specifications would be:

- 1 CPU with 1 GB RAM running Windows XP or greater version of Windows.
- Server to Simulate the ATM system and Database.
- Enough hardware and cloud storage space to install and backup important project files in case of accidental lost or deletion of data.

1.8 Budget

The budget will only be required in the development phase for two things:

- The acquiring and usability of a PC.
- Fingerprint Scanner system.

1.9 Database of Bank

Database of bank means it has all records and information about the user. It consists of users info such as name, bank id, bank accounts, account type and so on. This technology is addition to past technology with addition of users fingerprint which makes this technology efficient and secure.

1.10 Users Fingerprint

Users fingerprint is also a part of the database. These fingerprints are required when there is need to carry out any transaction. Every transaction is validated by fingerprints of the corresponding user. While carrying out transactions every user needs to SCAN his/her fingerprint on the machine.

1.10.1 Transaction Authentication

This is the step which authenticates the transaction i.e. whether valid or invalid user is carrying out the transaction through his/her fingerprints and this step makes transactions process secure and safe.

1.11 Functional Requirements

The designed interface and backend of the web portal will redefine the automated teller machine having:

1. A device used to detect and store fingerprints.
2. A customer input console mainly keyboards and display that is used for interaction with the customer, entering information and filling text boxes etc.

1.11.1 Facility of aborting transaction

A customer must be able to abort a transaction in progress by pressing the cancel key instead of responding to a request from the machine.

1.11.2 Email code format

The email provided should be of proper format and contain @ symbols.

1.11.3 Facility of Email re-entering

If the customer's email is invalid, the customer will be required to re-enter the email information before a specific transaction can be proceeded.

1.11.4 Denial of specific services, if Email goes wrong

If the customer is unable to successfully enter the email address, the service would be denied for the particular users.

1.11.5 Register finger

Put your finger on top of the device and allow it to record the fingerprint.

1.11.6 Facility of re-entering the finger

If the client's fingerprint is unacceptable, the customer will be essential to re-enter the impression before an operation can proceed.

1.11.7 Denial of service, if fingerprint goes wrong

If the customer is unsuccessful in enrolling his/her fingerprint after three tries, the service would be denied for that specific user until the timeout.

1.12 Non-Functional Requirements

There are some requirements that can be said to be non-functional in nature. Specifically, in these terms the constraints the system must obey are also called the qualities of the system. Other various forms of non-functional requirements are service requirements and non-behavioural requirements.

1.12.1 Scope

The scope of this project is to allow the user to get secure transactions and account access with the best scope of security transactions out there.

1.12.2 Functionality

The system includes multiple functionality with access to Deposited Amount, Withdrawn, Transferred, Receipt is generated and User has complete access to his account with some limitations.

1.12.3 Usability

The Web portal or interface is independent of the user's skills. Non-technical users are also able to use the system with ease. The interface follows all the basic principles of Human Computer Interaction.

1.12.4 Reliability

The system is reliable to not make any human errors with lag and error debug compatibility. The system shows confirmation of reliable use and information tracking.

1.12.5 Performance

The performance is independent of the user and completely depends on the device for execution. The interface and software runs at optimal performance on all supported browsers and multiple platforms.

1.12.6 Security

The fingerprint provided by the user to the system requires complete security and all information for these expense and purposes is secured with end-to-end encryption system. The Automated system must not store the

information or data in its database, for that reason a database is created external to the users limitations.

1.13 Front End Description

The Front-end interface will be fully dependent on .Net framework platform, with HTML and C sharp as the programming linguistic due to these reasons:

1. Flexible interface that is non-technical and easy to use.
2. User information is secured and customizable.
3. The system operates on good performance and is highly reliable.
4. Interface is based on the principles of Human Computer Interaction and has been made to be used at the best of its design.

1.14 Back End Description

In the process of database creation and development we are using MySQL Server- side database due to the following reasons:

1. Inherent support and complete compatibility with .NET platform.
2. Elastic, Accessible and vigorous database architecture.
3. This system is preferred and used by innovative leading companies worldwide.
4. Easy to manage and secure data protection.

1.15 Login Use Case I

Figure 1.1: Use case 1

Use Case ID	1
Title	Log-In
Description	The User will authenticate and make a transaction using Biometric Fingerprint
Primary Actor	Customer
Pre-Condition	Customer must provide with a valid Fingerprint or Card to log-In
Post-Condition	Account will be created successfully, or the User will be logged in

Table 1.1: Use case 1

1.16 Sign Up Use Case II

Figure 1.2: Use Case 2

Use Case ID	2
Title	Sign Up
Description	User-Administrator Will Sign In to access both portal.
Primary Actor	User-Customer-Administrator.
Pre-Condition	Account must be created (Sign Up).
Post-Condition	User-Administrator can use the system.

Figure 1.2: Use Case 2

1.17 Authentication Use Case III

Figure 1.3: Use case 3

Use Case ID	3
Title	Deposit
Description	User will sign in and deposit amount into his account
Primary Actor	Registered Users-Customers
Pre-Condition	User must be Sign In
Post-Condition	User will use the system and deposit amount

Table 1.3: Use case 3

Use Case ID	4
Title	With-draw
Description	User will sign in and with-draw amount from his/her account
Primary Actor	Registered Users-Customers
Pre-Condition	User must be Sign In and has some amount into his/her account
Post-Condition	User will use the system and with-draw amount

Table 1.4: Use case 4

Use Case ID	5
Title	Transfer
Description	User will sign in and transfer amount from his/her account to other account
Primary Actor	Registered Users-Customers
Pre-Condition	User must be Sign In and has some amount into his/her account to transfer
Post-Condition	User will use the system and transfer amount from his/her account

Table 1.5: Use case 5

1.18 Our Commitment

Our collective efforts in developing a fingerprint-based ATM system showcase our commitment to enhancing security and user experience in financial transactions. This approach adds a robust layer of protection against unauthorized access and identity theft. By streamlining the authentication process and eliminating the need for traditional methods, we contribute to a more secure and convenient future for banking. Our work has the potential to influence industry standards for secure transactions[1].

DESIGN DOCUMENT

2.1 System Architecture

The system has many basic functionalities of a traditional Automated Transaction System but does not require the Card or PIN code like in the traditional systems. It also has a draw back that if the current designed prototype system does not have a valid fingerprint identification due to any number of cases it can result in not being able to log into the system.

2.1.1 Design Constraints

The specific constraints in terms of design can Be specified as internet connection is an important constraint in running the basic web portal needed to execute the system capabilities. As all systems need data from the database, so in terms an internet connection is necessary. Database is shared between the systems and secure encryption on the user end and secure decryption on the server side is put into action. The web portal and the end system will be constrained by the capacity of internet and database used. Moreover, no specified device is ready for these systems as all devices or platform in support of the latest system can execute the browser capabilities to run this application. The design also functions for a module that matches fingerprints.

2.1.2 Sequence Diagram

Sequence diagram is used to show interaction between different object of the system. Web Sequence Diagram is tool used to draw the sequence diagram.

2.1.3 Login Sequence Diagram

The following is the sequence diagram of the Login into an Application. It tell the sequence of how to login into an Application.

2.1.4 Sign Up Sequence Diagram

The following is the sequence diagram of the Login into an Application. It tell the sequence of how to login into an Application.

2.2 Software Interface

The software being operated on the fingerprint scanner has to provide:

- The software that is being used by multiple banks.
- Networking software used to correspond with the device.

The detailed specification of the software interface is in detail not needed to be specified in this document.

2.3 Communication Interface

As long as the performance requirement is specified, there is no need to restrict the fingerprint scanner to operate on a single or specified network protocol.

2.4 Performance Requirements

2.4.1 Performance requisite I

In case of failure the error message should be displayed for at least 30 seconds.

2.4.2 Performance requisite II

In the case/scenario that there is no response from server due to invalid credentials or no record found in database after/within 2 minutes the card/fingerprint is disallowed with an error message.

2.4.3 Performance requisite III

Each system or bank may be dispensation transactions from several Fingerprint based scanner on the similar occasion.

2.5 Other Requirements

The Biometric Fingerprint based transaction system scanner must be able to use several data formats according to some of the data formats that are provided by the databases of different systems or banks. A common transaction should have all the properties of a Database transaction or data retrieval (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, Durability).

Figure 2.1: Use Case Diagram

Figure 2.2: ER Diagram

Figure 2.3: Data Flow Diagram

ATM UML Collaboration Diagram

Figure 2.4: Collaboration Diagram

Figure 2.5: Activity Diagram

This is the activity diagram of the transaction portal, it tells that how the activities will be carried out. The whole activity of the application is summarized in the following diagram.

Figure 2.6.1: Sequence Diagram 1

The following is the sequence diagram of the Sign up information. As you can see from the figure above, the user interacts with three basic entities of the transaction system. The most important Sign up information provided to the system is enrollement of users fingerprint, when the fingerprint and email are verified then the information is generated and account is successfully created.

Figure 2.6.2: Sequence Diagram 2

The following is the sequence diagram of the Log In Screen. As you can see from the figure above, the user interacts with three basic entities of the transaction system. The most important Login information provided to the system is identification of fingerprint, when the fingerprint and email are verified then the information is generated and the user is Logged In.

Figure 2.6.3: Sequence Diagram 3

The following is the sequence diagram of the Deposited Amount. As you can see from the figure above, the user interacts with three basic entities of the transaction system. When the user is successfully Logged In to his/her account, the user can perform a deposit amount function. However, If the user enters a negative amount is redirected to the same page. An email is generated if this process is successful.

Figure 2.6.4: Sequence Diagram 4

The following is the sequence diagram of the Withdrawn Amount. As you can see from the figure above, the user interacts with three basic entities of The transaction system. When the user is successfully Logged In to his/her account, the user can perform a withdraw amount function. Moreover, If user enters the amount which is not present in his/her account then the user is redirected to the same page. An email is generated when the transaction is successful.

Figure 2.6.5: Sequence Diagram 5

The following is the sequence diagram of the Transfer Amount. When the user is successfully Logged In to his/her account, the user can perform a transfer amount function, in which the user has to provide correct account information and amount. An email is generated when the amount transfer is successful.

Figure 2.7: State Chart Diagram

Testing Document

System testing of software or hardware is testing conducted on a complete, integrated system to evaluate the systems compliance with its specified requirements. Software testing technique is the process of checking and evaluating whether the system is performing the tasks it was supposed to do or not. The following are some of the software testing techniques.:

- Usability Testing.
- Interface Testing.
- Performance Testing.
- Compatibility Testing.

3.1 Graphical User Interface Testing

Our Web portal redefines simplicity in a way that the user can access his account and credentials, including creating a new account through just the introductory page of our portal. Everything is defined on the portal to help the user and guide him through the process. Even the users with no knowledge of the system or skills required to log into their accounts are guided through the process and are able to log in.

3.2 Usability Testing

Our application and system upon which it is being carried out, requires no technical experience to use. The system we built has a Web portal through which the user can access his account, this only requires physical implementation by which the user implements his fingerprint on the system and can hence log into the system to access all the functionalities of his account.

3.3 Software Performance Testing

Our Fingerprint based ATM system requires no exceptional hardware capabilities, the system has minimal response time, low system hardware

utilization which accounts for great overall performance in the system. The system is easy to maintain and requires no external help in maintaining. In the unfortunate case of system failure, the recoverability of the system requires it to be restored to the default/original state in which the system was created. The system is also reliable because it responds to user in similar way as it was designed. The system usability can be defined in an easy way as descriptive definition of everything is provided. Our system security is the main measure of its success as the system is secure than the traditional systems and requires authentication of physical fingerprint and email. Data integrity is authenticated and encrypted using 3D map, so data cannot be manipulated in any way by the hackers or data integrity evaluators.

3.4 Compatibility Testing

The basic prototype of our system operates in such a way that the web portal requires minimal hardware capabilities and supports all the latest browsers for loading the web portal including but not limited to, Firefox, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, Opera, etc. The portal is compatible to run on all devices that include the browser and internet compatibility with a fingerprint device attached to detect the physical print of the User. The platform version is 1.0 and requires devices specification of at least a biometric fingerprint detection device and a core Atom or later compatibility of processor support with latest browser integration support system.

3.5 Exception Handling

- Exception handling is integrated in the following modules of the application.
- Login: Imperative to sign up in case of registration.
- Sign In: Requires input within defined parameters.
- Fingerprint: Required to match both the input or exceptions are generated in the system.
- Account Info: Appropriate account info no provided will generate an error message within the system.

3.6 Load Testing

The load testing was performed on few platforms and devices but no such behaviour in time, requirement gathering, or load balancing was detected that we could perform a load testing variation on the system. The system however showed nominal changes in performance (hardly noticeable) and performed with no errors and lag (cause for debugging) on any particular system.

3.7 Installation Testing

Since the prototype of our main system is operating on web-based applications, it requires no installation on multiple systems. Moreover, depending on the Web portal it can hence be installed/operated on different platforms each of which has an internet functionality and browser or portal support. Installing the system or in this case executing it on a platform only requires internet and browser support on any compatible device with input modules to input information.

3.8 Testcases

Test Case id	001
Function to be tested	Sign Up
Initial State	“Application/System” must be installed
Input	Enter valid user credentials and fingerprint identification
Expected Output	User must be register successfully
Actual Output	User logged in successfully and home page displays
Status	Positive Pass

Table 3.1: Test case 1 (sign up I)

Test Case id	002
Function to be tested	Sign Up
Initial State	“Application/System” must be installed
Input	Enter invalid user credentials and fingerprint identification
Expected Output	User must not be register successfully
Actual Output	User redirected to the same page
Status	Negative Pass

Table 3.2: Test case 2 (sign up II)

Test Case id	003
Function to be tested	Login
Initial State	User must already be registered in the System/Application
Input	Enter valid user credentials and correct fingerprint identification
Expected Output	User must be login successfully
Actual Output	User logged in successfully
Status	Positive Pass

Table 3.3: Test case 3 (Log in I)

Test Case id	004
Function to be tested	Login
Initial State	User must already be registered in the System/Application
Input	Enter invalid user credentials and/or incorrect fingerprint identification
Expected Output	User must not be logged in successfully
Actual Output	Error message generates, and user redirected to the same page
Status	Negative Pass

Table 3.4: Test case 4 (Log in II)

Test Case id	005
Function to be tested	Deposit
Initial State	User must be logged into System/Application
Input	Enter correct amount to deposit in account
Expected Output	Amount has been deposited and email generates successfully
Actual Output	Email has been successfully generated into user's email
Status	Positive Pass

Table 3.5: Test case 5 (Deposit I)

Test Case id	006
Function to be tested	Deposit
Initial State	User must be logged into System/Application
Input	If negative amount is entered into the by the user that exceeds defined parameters within the system
Expected Output	Amount has not been deposited and an error message is displayed
Actual Output	Error message displays and user is redirected to same page
Status	Negative Pass

Table 3.6: Test case 6 (Deposit II)

Test Case id	007
Function to be tested	With-Draw
Initial State	User must be logged into System/Application
Input	User enters the correct amount that are already present in his/her account
Expected Output	Amount with-drawl is completed, and email generates successfully
Actual Output	Email has been successfully generated into user's email
Status	Positive Pass

Table 3.7: Test case 7 (With-Draw I)

Test Case id	008
Function to be tested	With-Draw
Initial State	User must be logged into System/Application
Input	User enters the incorrect amount that is not present in his/her account
Expected Output	Amount for with-drawl is not completed, and an error message is displayed
Actual Output	Email is not generated, and user is redirected to same page
Status	Negative Pass

Table 3.8: Test case 8 (With-Draw II)

Test Case id	009
Function to be tested	Transfer
Initial State	User must be logged into System/Application
Input	User enters the correct account number and amount that is present in his/her account
Expected Output	Amount transfer is completed, and email generates successfully
Actual Output	Email has been successfully generated into user's email
Status	Positive Pass

Table 3.9: Test case 9 (Transfer I)

Test Case id	010
Function to be tested	Transfer
Initial State	User must be logged into System/Application
Input	User enters the incorrect account number and/or amount that is present in his/her account
Expected Output	Amount transfer is not completed, and no email is generated
Actual Output	Email is not generated successfully, and user is redirected to same page
Status	Negative Pass

Table 3.10: Test case 10 (Transfer II)

3.9 Testing and Results

The test results indicate that our system is efficient in running, accuracy is mostly dependent on the user. Hence the results can be expressed and represented in this way:

3.9.1 Performance Testing:

Technology stack was chosen which itself has proven capabilities so there were no worries about poor performance as user load increases. .Net framework runs all the latest sites with support for all media and Browser on multiple platform devices.

3.9.2 Security Testing:

Security testing was performed at the end of implementation, as the target audience of the system enables only register users to Login and use the system. There are also other security measures installed for security enhancement inside the system which prevents unauthorized user from accessing the system and is an integral part of security testing.

3.9.3 Non-Functional Testing:

As per the requirements for system performance, a few of the basic non-functional testing characteristics were tested which are mentioned as follows:

- Reliability Testing.
- Maintainability Testing.
- Performance Testing.
- Exception Handling.
- Efficiency Testing.
- Load Testing.

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